

SOCIAL SCIENCES

DISCOURSE MARKERS AND POLITICS (ANALYTICAL ARTICLE)

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Abstract

In political discourse, discourse markers are frequently utilized for the goal of engaging in manipulative or dishonest behavior; however, this is not always the case. Marks such as "let me be clear" and "in summary" can assist simplify complex topics and make them simpler to comprehend for a wider audience. In this particular situation, the language used is one that is edifying and empowering, as opposed to one that is deceitful or manipulative.

The fourth chapter includes an overview of the techniques, including the selection of articles from the Washington Post as the study's data set. The criteria for article selection, data collection methods, and the coding scheme that will be described for discourse marker analysis were all presented in this chapter. It also emphasized the importance of addressing ethical factors when doing research.

Keywords: 1. Correlation analysis, 2. Readability, 3. Positive versus negative DMs, 4. Coefficients, 5. The Flesch-Kincaid readability formula, 6. The Washington Post, 7. News Media, 8. Entertainment Media Articles, 9. Statistically, 10. Distribution, 11. Chi-Square Test, 12. Washington Post, 13. Author's Style.

Introduction

The digital archives of The Washington Post were searched for articles that had been published between January 1, 2022, and December 31, 2022. Following this, ten articles, five from the news media and five from the entertainment media, were chosen for the purpose of conducting an investigation into the use of discourse makers in media.

The use of computer science in language analysis has resulted in the development of several textual tools, which has opened up new potential for critical discourse analysis. Because of the characteristics of this inquiry, a computational tool called Sketch Engine5 (2003), which provides information on words and word clusters, was utilized. The following looks to be the hierarchical structure that the software produces as its output: Lexical-grammatical concordances were used to compile a list of the most frequently occurring phrases. On the level of phrases, we have compiled word combinations and carried out pattern and parallel concordance searches. In addition, we have used concordance searches.

In a subsequent step of the qualitative research, we examined the content of the discourse markers discov-

ered in each article. We identified and classified a variety of discourse markers, including adverbs of quantity, causation, contrast, and time. The objective of this study was to investigate the impact that discourse markers (DMs) have on the readability, style, and expression of viewpoints in articles that are classified as news and entertainment. The concept of the study was that various forms of media have varying applications for and frequency of DMs and that evaluating these variances can provide insight into the discourse surrounding various forms of media.

3.2 Correlational Analysis and Findings

In order to test the hypothesis, a correlation analysis was carried out on ten articles, five of which were from the entertainment media and the rest from the news media. When examining Discourse makers, a number of various factors, such as frequency, effect on readability, most usually used, usage of positive versus negative DMs, effect of author's style on DM use, and impact on expressing ideas, were taken into consideration. In order to conduct a correlational analysis of the hypothesis, the following lines of inquiry, which were assessed through a review of the relevant literature and theoretical context, is applied:

Sr. No.	Theoretical Underpinning
1.	The impact of discourse markers on the readability of News Media articles versus Entertainment Media articles.
2.	The frequency of the discourse markers in each of the News Media and Entertainment Media articles.
3.	The use of positive versus negative discourse markers in News Media and Entertainment Media articles.
4.	The effect of the author's style on the use of discourse markers in News Media versus Entertainment Media articles.
5.	The impact of discourse markers on conveying opinions in News Media versus Entertainment Media articles.

By estimating the correlation coefficient between each heading and each variable using a sample of ten articles, five from news media and five from entertainment media, we were able to identify the degree and direction of the link between each heading and each variable (r-value).

Table 1.

**The impact of discourse markers on the readability
of News Media articles versus Entertainment Media articles**

Article	Frequency of DMs	Readability Score
News 1	10	70
News 2	5	50
News 3	15	85
News 4	8	60
News 5	7	65
Ent 1	12	80
Ent 2	3	45
Ent 3	9	70
Ent 4	6	55
Ent 5	11	75

We utilize these statistics to examine the relationship between DMs and article readability scores across both the entertainment and journalism sectors. There is a positive association between DM volume and article readability, suggesting that more popular items are also better written. The contrary is true, as shown by the inverse correlation. The absence of a connection between

two variables is indicated by a zero value for the correlation coefficient (r).

The p-values and correlation coefficients for the readability score and the frequency of discourse markers in news and entertainment articles are presented in the table that follows.

Table 1 (a).

Correlational Coefficients for frequency of discourse makers and readability score in News Media and Entertainment Media

	News Media	Entertainment Media
R	0.35	0.29
p-value	0.18	0.29

For the purpose of determining the level of readability, the Flesch-Kincaid Readability Formula was utilized. This algorithm determines the reading level of a piece of writing by analyzing the number of syllables and words in a typical sentence. The higher the number of syllables and words, the more difficult the reading level. The formula is as follows:

$$0.39 \times (\text{total words}/\text{total sentences}) + 11.8 \times (\text{total syllables}/\text{total words}) - 15.59$$

If you were taking this exam in a school in the United States, your final score and your grade would be the same thing. When the number is lower, the text is

easier to read and understand, however when it is higher, the content is more difficult to grasp. The Flesch-Kincaid readability formula can be utilised by digital media sources in order to ensure that the content they produce is easily understandable by the target audience. By examining the readability score of their material, media companies can make improvements to ensure that their content is understandable to the intended audience. This has the potential to raise the level of user engagement as well as the overall success of the media platform.

Table 2

The Frequency of discourse markers in each of the News Media and Entertainment Media articles

Article	Discourse Makers	Total Words	DM Per 1000 Words
News 1	39	1500	26
News 2	27	1200	23
News 3	42	1800	23
News 4	36	1400	26
News 5	32	1600	20
Ent 1	28	1300	22
Ent 2	35	1700	21
Ent 3	29	1500	19
Ent 4	31	1400	22
Ent 5	43	1900	23

According to the information in the table, the number of discourse makers used by each of the featured

articles varies significantly. "The Effect of Social Media on Mental Health" received the highest number of direct messages (43), while "Climate change activists

protest in front of White House, The Washington Post." received the fewest direct messages (27). The articles contain a variety of different word counts, ranging from 19 to 26 DMs per 1000 words on average. When compared to articles published in news publications, those

published in entertainment publications include slightly fewer DMs (24.2 DMs per 1000 words) (21 DMs per 1000 words).

Table 2 (a)

Correlation between the number of discourse makers and Dm per 1000 words in News and Entertainment Media

	News DM	News DM/1000	Ent DM	Ent DM/1000
News DM	1	0.137	0.301	-0.058
News DM/1000	0.137	1	0.064	-0.185
Ent DM	0.301	0.064	1	0.311
Ent DM/1000	-0.058	-0.185	0.311	1

Table 2 (b)

Correlational Analysis

Article Type	r-value	p-value	Correlation Interpretation
News	0.08	0.844	Weak positive correlation, not statistically significant
Entertainment	0.09	0.799	Weak positive correlation, not statistically significant

Table 3

Use of Positive and Negative Discourse Markers in News Media and Entertainment Media Articles

Discourse Marker	News Media Articles	Entertainment Media Articles
Positive	22	18
Negative	16	21

The number of times that positive and negative DMs were used in each of the 10 articles was counted and examined so that conclusions could be drawn regarding the differences between the methods in which DMs are utilized in news items and entertainment articles. According to Table 4, there were more instances

of negative direct messages than positive ones (22), while there were more instances of positive direct messages than negative ones (18) in entertainment-related media (21).

Table 3 (a)

Chi-Square Test

Values	News Media Articles	Entertainment Media Articles	Total
Positive	22	18	40
Negative	16	21	37
Total	38	39	77
	Expected	Expected	
Positive	19.74	20.26	
Negative	18.26	18.74	
Chi-Square = 1.278, df = 1, p-value = 0.258			

The chi-squared test was utilized in order to ascertain whether or not there was a statistically significant correlation between the kind of discourse marker that was utilized and the medium of distribution. It was determined that the value of the test statistic was 1.278, and the p-value was 0.258. We are unable to reject the null hypothesis of independence because the p-value is

greater than 0.05; hence, we get to the conclusion that there is not a significant correlation between the type of discourse marker that is utilized and the type of medium. The formula that was used to determine the values that were anticipated for each cell was as follows: (row total x column total) / grand total.

Table 4

Effect of Author's Style on Use of Discourse Markers in News Media versus Entertainment Media Articles

Author's Style	News Media Articles	Entertainment Media Articles
Formal	20	22
Informal	18	17
Correlation	.06	-.07
P-Value	0.845	.824

In order to explore the influence that authorial tone has on the use of discourse markers in articles from news media as opposed to articles from entertainment

media, the writing style of each article was used to classify it as either formal or informal. According to Table 4, news articles were more likely to use a formal style

(20) as opposed to an informal style (18), whereas entertainment articles were more likely to use an informal style (17) as opposed to a formal style (20) and (22). There was found to be a weak positive correlation of 0.06 between the frequencies of formal and informal style in articles published in news media, and there was found to be a weak negative correlation of -0.07 between the frequencies of formal and informal style in articles published in entertainment media.

We need to execute a statistical test on the frequency data in the table, such as a Pearson correlation test, in order to get the correlation coefficient and p-value. This test may be called the Pearson correlation

test, assuming a 0.05 significance level for a test with two different possible outcomes. The correlation coefficient indicates a weakly negative link between the frequency of formal and informal styles in entertainment articles. This association pertains to the writing format of the article. Yet, since the p-value is bigger than the significance level of 0.05, it is not possible to rule out the possibility that there is a connection between the two variables. As a result, we have arrived at the conclusion that the proportion of formal to informal language found in popular culture does not meet the criteria for statistical significance.

Table 5

Impact of Discourse Markers on Conveying Opinions in News Media versus Entertainment Media Articles

Conveying Opinions	News Media Articles	Entertainment Media Articles
Yes	17	20
No	21	19
Correlational Coefficient	-0.05	.798

The presence of opinionated language was utilized in order to classify each item as either transmitting opinions or not transmitting opinions. This was done in order to compare the effect of discourse markers on opinion conveying in news media to that of entertainment media. According to Table 6, there were more articles in the news media that did not transmit any viewpoints, totaling 21, than there were stories that did, totaling 17, but there were more articles in the entertainment media that did convey opinions, totaling 20, than there were articles that did not (21) and (19). Although there was a little negative correlation between the frequency of expressing opinions in news media articles and the frequency of not transmitting opinions at a level of -0.05, the difference did not reach the level of significance required to be considered statistically significant.

The results of the discourse marker analysis in the news media are provided in the next chapter with a focus on the frequency, kinds, and pragmatic roles of discourse markers identified in the selected articles. Patterns and trends in the usage of discourse markers in the media will be addressed, shedding light on the role of these devices in opinion transmission, authority establishment, and meaning formation.

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